

Project Title	Global cooperation on FAIR data policy and practice
Project Acronym	WorldFAIR
Grant Agreement No	101058393
Instrument	HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ERA-01
Topic, type of action	HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ERA-01-41 HORIZON Coordination and Support Actions
Start Date of Project	2022-06-01
Duration of Project	24 months
Project Website	http://worldfair-project.eu

MS8 Biodiversity Workshop

Work Package	WP9
Lead Author (Org)	Joe Miller (GBIF)
Due Date	31.08.2023
Date	29.08.2023
Version	1.0 DRAFT NOT YET APPROVED BY THE EUROPEAN COMMISSION
DOI	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8283653

DRAFT NOT YET APPROVED BY THE EUROPEAN COMMISSION

Dissemination Level

- | | |
|-------------------------------------|--|
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> | PU: Public |
| <input type="checkbox"/> | PP: Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission) |
| <input type="checkbox"/> | RE: Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission) |
| <input type="checkbox"/> | CO: Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission) |

Table of contents

1. Introduction	3
2. The workshop	3
3. Feedback and next steps	5

1. Introduction

As part of WorldFAIR WP9, the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF) convened a workshop entitled “Unified data model for mobilizing and sharing collections data” at the annual meeting of the Society for the Preservation of Natural History Collections (SPNHC)¹. SPNHC is an international society whose mission is to improve the preservation, conservation and management of natural history collections to ensure their continuing value to society. A workshop proposal was submitted and approved via a SPNHC competitive process. The half day workshop on 29 May 2023 occurred during the SPNHC annual conference in San Francisco, California, USA.

The GBIF data model work, as described in WorldFAIR Deliverable 9.1², has a major focus on material specimens from natural history collections. SPNHC is a natural audience of GBIF users to test and get feedback on the developing Unified Data Model. SPNHC is a community that leads biodiversity collection standard development and, most importantly for GBIF, are the principal users of the GBIF data model as the meeting attendees are collections data managers.

The goal of the workshop was to receive feedback on the Unified Data Model during this important community standards meeting. This took place by interacting with workers with varying degrees of experience with Darwin Core, the foundation of the current data model. These interactions will help to guide the WP09 team with regard to how much complexity it is feasible to build into the model before it becomes more of a hindrance to data sharing than a benefit.

2. The workshop

The title of the workshop was: ‘[Unified data model for mobilizing and sharing collections data](#)’. The workshop abstract is quoted here:

“Since 2021, GBIF has been engaging the community in a project to develop a new data model. Diversifying the data model allows the community to explore approaches to support the publication of richer, more complex types of biodiversity data. In this workshop, we will examine some of the many possible ways to mobilise and share your collections data using the emerging unified data model. The agenda for this workshop will evolve as the work on the data model continues to take shape over the next six months. A complementary workshop will also be offered on making your collections data discoverable.”

The workshop agenda was as follows:

¹ <https://spnhc.org/>

² <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7849241>

1. Welcome/Introductions - 10 min
2. Introduction to the emerging data model and relevant case studies - 45 min
3. Community demonstrations for modelling collections data/results of the small grants program - 50 min
4. Break - 30 min
5. Preparing data for publication - 90 min (participants are encouraged to bring their own data for practice, but sample data will be available)
6. Conclusion - 15 min

The workshop lead was Laura Anne Russell, lead trainer at GBIF. Data model content lead was John R. Wieczorek, the GBIF contractor for the WorldFAIR WP9, and lead on the Unified Data model development, and Marie Grosjean, GBIF Data Products Officer, also taught during the workshop.

Thirty-one people participated in the workshop of which only 9 had previous experience with the Unified Data Model work. The attendees were from 10 countries with the largest representation from the United States where the workshop was held.

The workshop was led off by an overview presentation³ of the status of the Unified Data Model by Wieczorek. The workshop also included talks by community leaders that have tested the Unified data model on collection-based specimen data. Some of these results are also further described in WorldFAIR Deliverable 9.1⁴.

- Andy Bentley, Specify Data Database and University of Kansas. Presentation video: https://drive.google.com/file/d/1bpCLBz7JZz7j8nmaej1a7B8BGEWnPdm/view?usp=drive_link
- Laura Rocha, Symbiota, Arizona State University. Presentation slides: https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1pKI87FvXUiUz3WEyNF9vk8Z1v38ONasK/edit?usp=drive_link&oid=117502443904659677254&rtpof=true&sd=true
- Katie Pierson, Symbiota, Arizona State University
- Jörg Holetschek, Botanical Garden and Botanical Museum Berlin. Presentation video: https://drive.google.com/file/d/1jSzUKn3Ow-VMctaayBTOUShV3QJGLkgX/view?usp=drive_link

The workshop participants then broke into three groups, loosely based on their experience level with data publishing to GBIF. The goal was to be able to get feedback based on discussions at their

³https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1e9S7DBWQW2nKaw4TONqNomZG-2FQb7-jnaxlGoLpM_Y/edit?usp=drive_link

⁴ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7849241>

expertise level so that all could participate. Group 1 had no or very little experience in publishing data; Group 2 had some experience but not expert level; and Group 3 had high level expertise with the most potential for impactful feedback on the data model.

3. Feedback and next steps

The results of the group work were as expected by the WP team and are discussed in D9.1. Key points include:

- There is still much capacity variation among GBIF community members on how to publish data;
- Data model implementation must be accommodated by training;
- The data model provides improvements in collection data utilisation.

The data model development must be designed and taught at multiple levels to accommodate the varying expertise and needs in the community. In general, standards users - especially at smaller institutions - use them as part of a much larger work portfolio. Their use of standards must be made easy as they may only actively engage with standards a few days per month or year. Other users - for example, at larger museums - would use standards almost daily and will be more able to advise on the standard implementation details. Therefore there is no shortcut to development and training of standards; users must be engaged for the model to meet their needs and expectations.

Given this feedback, our next steps for WP09 are the following activities:

- Expand data model to new data types;
- Begin new data model development phase with ecological data;
- Collaboration with WP10 on data model advancement for Agriculture biodiversity in particular plant pollinator data;
- Implementation of data publication protocols based on the feedback with careful monitoring and adaptation to user needs;
- Develop material catalogue user access to data published to the new data model;
- Develop training materials to be implemented within the GBIF training curriculum.

GBIF continues to include data model development in our annual work programme for 2024. This will continue to future years and beyond the WorldFAIR project. We have now received valuable feedback on the model for use by the natural history community. For that community we are

DRAFT NOT YET APPROVED BY THE EUROPEAN COMMISSION

moving to the development of the publishing protocols and the material catalogue from which the modelled data can be accessed in unique ways.

As for the unified data model, it is time to design and community-test new aspects of the model that are relevant to different members of the GBIF community. Primarily this will be the ecological community, including the biotic interactions important to plant pollination. This explicitly includes collaboration with WorldFAIR WP10 on data model advancement for agricultural biodiversity and in particular, plant pollinator data.

